

POSSIBILITIES AND LIMITS OF METAL REINFORCED REFRACTORY

SILICIDES ESPECIALLY MOLYBDENUM DISILICIDE

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Abstract

The paper describes the fabrication and the mechanical properties of Nb-wire reinforced MoSi_2 . This material combination exhibits the same high oxidation resistance as hot pressed MoSi_2 and with a matrix modified by 10 Mol % MoGe_2 quasi plastic fracture behaviour.

The reinforcement by 40 Vol % of niobium-wires leads to a flexural strength of 700 MPa, twice of the best sintered MoSi_2 -qualities. An amount of 10 Mol % MoGe_2 in the initial MoSi_2 -matrix improves the adhesion of the Nb-wires in the brittle ceramic matrix. It improves also the thermoshock resistance by the formation of GeO_2 containing SiO_2 -glasses at the surface of the composite.

Finally the diffusion phenomena in the system $\text{Nb}/\text{Mo}(\text{Si},\text{Ge})_2$ are discussed.

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1. Advanced MoSi₂-ceramics

It is well known that glassy silica surface layers on high temperature materials are excellent barriers against oxidation attack at high temperatures, because of their very low oxygen permeation rate. Fig.1 shows oxidation rates versus temperature for the commonly used silicon ceramics.

Molybdenum disilicide (MoSi₂) is known as a high melting intermetallic compound for almost eighty years. It has found industrial application as a material for electric heating, being a metal-like conductor with an exceptional oxidation resistance up to 1900 K in air. This is due to the formation of a self-healing protective silica glass layer. The latter depends on the volatilisation of the simultaneously formed MoO₃. Oxidation without MoO₃ volatilisation causes fast intergranular oxidation with severe material damage, the so-called 'MoSi₂-pest'. This low-temperature oxidation can be avoided by various means, e.g. diminishing the porosity. A detailed review about MoSi₂ and its application was published by J. Schlichting in 1978 (6).

The present paper is concerned with the modification of the MoSi₂ matrix with small amounts of MoGe₂ for improving the above mentioned low-temperature oxidation behaviour. Former studies of the combination MoSi₂/MoGe₂ by K. Zeitsch (9) showed that the 'pest' reaction could be suppressed by the addition of MoGe₂. Additionally solved by this combination are the crack formation and destruction of the glassy surface layer during cyclic heating and cooling, because small amounts of GeO₂ in SiO₂ considerably increase the thermal expansion coefficient and decrease the viscosity compared with that of pure SiO₂.

The first step towards reinforcement of MoSi₂ by niobium wires was made by D. Kehr (7). Before then MoSi₂ was investigated as a sintered material or as protective coating on refractory metals like Ta, Nb, W or Mo in air at high temperatures. The lifetime of such cermets is controlled only by Si losses caused by the rate of diffusion of silicon from the MoSi₂ layer into the basic material. Any local destruction of the protective layer by mechanical influences such as impacts or by crack formation, however causes a catastrophic total oxidation of the body as a whole.

This behaviour gave rise to the idea of separating the refractory metals into small discrete units pursuing the end saving the main body even if some of these discrete units should be destroyed by oxidation. The most promising access to the realization of this idea was the use of the refractory metals as wires in a MoSi₂-matrix (10).

2. Theory of 'inverse' composites

A basic model for the so-called 'inverse' composites was introduced in 1978 by one of us (2), shown in Fig.2. As ordinate he used the ratio of strain to failure of matrix versus fibre, as abscissa the ratio YOUNG's modulus of matrix. The left side of the plot indicates the well-known situation, where a soft material is reinforced by a high modulus fibre.

In the case of niobium wire reinforced MoSi₂, the YOUNG's modulus of the fibres is lower than that of the matrix, and the strain to failure of the matrix is smaller than that of the ductile fibre. Although one cannot expect a reinforcing effect, we found experimentally that the brittle matrix/ductile wire composite shows improved flexural strength and fracture behaviour.

The philosophy of reinforcement of brittle ceramic materials is different from the reinforcement of ductile matrix materials like polymers and metals, where the strength of the composite is only controlled by the strain to

Fig. 1: Oxidation rate versus temperature of the commonly used silicon ceramics

Fig. 2: Final conclusions on reinforcement of brittle ceramics. Predicted reinforcement for any possible combination

Fig. 3: Stress-strain behaviour of unidirectional reinforced composites with brittle matrix

failure of the fibre (Fig.3). Reinforcement of brittle matrix materials by brittle fibres is a further basically different method. Fig.3 shows schematically these three fundamental cases.

3. Diffusion mechanism in MoSi₂/refractory metal cermets during oxidation

MoSi₂ is a high oxidation resistant but extremely brittle and hard intermetallic material. The transition temperature of its brittleness was measured by us in the area about 1000°C (1). The outstanding oxidation resistance up to 1650°C is based on the formation of a self healing SiO₂-glass layer during oxidation. The growth of the glassy or partially crystalline SiO₂ protective layer is controlled by the slow molecular diffusion of oxygen through the primarily formed SiO₂ layer. Besides a small mass loss by sublimating of MoO₃ during the first step of oxidation only a selective oxidation of silicon takes place (Fig.4). For the improvement of the extreme brittleness of MoSi₂ the idea was to reinforce the material with high melting, ductile metals as for example Mo, Nb or Ta.

Former diffusion studies (2) with the diffusion pair Mo/MoSi₂ showed that MoSi₂ in contact with Mo substrates forms silicides with a lower silicon content. Both reactions, oxidation and diffusion to the substrate, consume silicon from the MoSi₂. The layer growth corresponds to a parabolic law. Fig.4 shows the SiO₂ and Mo₅Si₃ layer thickness as a function of the square root of the oxidation time at 1300°C, 1450°C and 1600°C. The silicide consumption by oxidation is indicated on a larger scale on the left-hand side. This chemical attack can almost be neglected in comparison with the silicon loss by diffusion to the substrate.

As reinforcement material niobium was selected, because the diffusion of silicon (Fig.5) through an interlayer of (Mo, Nb)₅Si₃ is much lower than through Mo₅Si₃ (3). Although the chemical compatibility can be regarded as solved by this combination, there remains the problem of the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients between the SiO₂ layer ($\alpha = 0.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$) and the Mo₅Si₃ interlayer ($\alpha = 6.7-7.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$) (2f). This problem was solved by chemical modification of the outer oxide layer. An addition of MoGe₂ to the MoSi₂ will increase the thermal expansion coefficient of the resulting oxide layer at the surface. The viscosity of the oxide layer decreases simultaneously. Both effects avoid thermal stresses between the oxide layer and the substrate during thermal cycling. Fig.6 shows the enormous increase of the thermal expansion coefficient by addition of a small amount GeO₂ to SiO₂ (4) from initial $0.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ (pure SiO₂) to about $6 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ according to Mo₅Si₃ (v.s.).

4. Fabrication of Nb-wire reinforced MoSi₂

As fabrication method for the Nb-wire reinforced MoSi₂ samples hotpressing was used (Fig.7). A female die was filled alternatively with silicide powder mixture and prepreps of niobium wires, prepared by a slurry technique (5). The heating was performed by an induction coil. The pressure in the arrangement is slowly increased until the sintering temperature is reached, in order to avoid the deformation of the Nb-wires during the hotpressing procedure. The progress of densification during hotpressing is shown in Fig.8. We can see, that an increasing content of MoGe₂ diminishes sintering temperatures.

Fig.9 shows the polished micrograph of a Nb-wire reinforced Mo(Si, Ge)₂ composite. The MoGe₂ content is 10 Mol%, the Nb-wire content 40 Vol%. We can see the horizontal arrangement of the Nb-layers combined with an inhomogeneous porosity. Between the original prepreg layers a better densification was obtained than inside the layers indicating anisotropic pressure distribution.

Fig. 4 Diffusion phenomena during oxidation of MoSi_2/Mo cermets

Fig. 5 Schematic sequence of diffusion layers for MoSi_2/Mo and MoSi_2/Nb

Fig. 6 Thermal expansion coefficient of the system $\text{SiO}_2/\text{GeO}_2$

Fig. 7 Hot pressing arrangement for Nb-wire reinforced MoSi_2

Fig. 8 Bulk density of $\text{Mo}(\text{Si,Ge})_2$ -mixtures after hot pressing (1 h, 200 bar)

Fig. 9 Polished micrograph of Nb-wire reinforced $\text{Mo}(\text{Si,Ge})_2$

5. Mechanical properties and fracture behaviour of Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ composites

The fracture surface of Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ composites is shown in Fig.10. During deflection the Nb-wires are deformed and their diameter decreased with simultaneous discharging of the wire from the matrix. Up to now it is not possible to find the bench-mark of the wires for calculating the elongation and resulting Young's modulus for the niobium after hotpressing.

The stress-strain- diagram of the system Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ is shown in Fig.11. The highest Young's modulus has been found for pure MoSi₂. Addition of MoGe₂ leads to a slightly greater deflection with the same flexural strength of 320 MPa. Reinforcement of pure MoSi₂ enlarges insignificantly the load for crack starting to the first Nb-wire² layer. The crack propagation to the following layer is the last step before failure of the composite. Addition of MoGe₂ to the matrix leads to 'quasi' ductile behaviour, shown for a fibre content of 23 and 40 Vol% niobium. Addition of 40 Vol% Nb-wires increases the flexural strength to the maximum value of 700 MPa.

The reinforcement of Mo(Si,Ge)₂ with only one prepreg layer showed a remarkable increase of strength. The increase is much higher than expected for the small amount of wires. It can be seen in Fig. 12 that the maximum increase of more than 50 % against pure matrix material can be achieved, if the reinforcing layer of niobium wires is near the surface at the tensile side of the test specimen. The maximum increase was found with distances between surface and wire axis of the double wire diameter. All specimens showed brittle fracture behaviour after the single layer of niobium wires was broken.

Fig. 13 shows the flexural strength of samples with different germanide content in the matrix versus wire fraction. One can see an increasing strength with increasing wire fraction. Reinforced samples without germanide in the matrix show a maximal increase of strength up to 50 %, and such with a matrix content of 10 % MoGe₂ lead to an improvement of more than 130 % compared with unreinforced molybdenum disilicide. Higher germanide contents in the matrix lead to a smaller increase of strength. The growing brittleness of niobium is caused by the diffusion of germanium into the wires, mainly at the grain boundaries.

Different fracture surfaces of Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ with and without MoGe₂ addition are shown in Fig.14. The fracture surface in case of MoSi₂ reveals no remarkable difference between wires and matrix. The crack propagation velocity is retarded in the Nb-wires as demonstrated with SEM of the intercrystalline fracture texture (Fig.14, second row, left hand side). On the other hand the addition of MoGe₂ leads to crack bridging wires after the crack reached the first layer by delamination in the (Nb,Mo)₅(Si,Ge)₃ interlayer formed by diffusion during hot pressing.

The different mechanical properties of the (Mo,Nb)₅Si₃ and (Mo,Nb)₅(Si,Ge)₃ interlayers are shown in Fig.14 at the bottom. These different interlayers have been analyzed by EMPA. The line scans of the diffusion zone of two composites produced under the same conditions (1650 °C, 1 h) are presented in Fig.15. We can remark the greater diffusion coefficient of silicon against the metals. Between the parent materials there is the diffusion zone Me₅Si₃ with a continuous exchange of Mo with Nb beginning from the matrix to the niobium wire. More complicated is the line scan with MoGe₂ in the matrix. Showing nearly the same distribution for Mo, Nb and Si we can see an enrichment of Ge. This fact is shown better in Fig.16, the X-ray scan pictures of these four elements. Including the different scale the diffusion zone without Ge is 20 % larger than with Ge.

Fig. 10 Fracture surface of Nb-wire reinforced $\text{Mo}(\text{Si},\text{Ge})_2$

Fig. 11 Stress-strain diagram of pure and Nb-wire reinforced $\text{Mo}(\text{Si},\text{Ge})_2$

Fig. 12 Flexural strength of composites, reinforced with only one prepreg layer at the tensile side, as a function of the distance of the axis of the reinforcing wires to the surface

Fig. 13 Flexural strength of samples with different germanide content in the matrix versus wire fraction

Fig. 14 Crack surface in pure MoSi_2 (left hand side) and MoGe_2 (right hand side) containing composites, reinforced with niobium wires

Fig. 15 Analysis of the distribution of the elements in the diffusion zone between Nb-wire and matrix after hot pressing.
 Top: Line scan of $(\text{Mo,Nb})_5\text{Si}_3$ interlayer
 Bottom: Line scan of $(\text{Mo,Nb})_5(\text{Si,Ge})_3$ interlayer

Fig. 16 X-ray scan pictures of the elements Mo, Nb, Si and Ge in the diffusion zone between matrix and niobium wire

Fig. 17 Specific weight change of pure bulk material with different germanide content at 1000°C under air (short-time measurement)

6. Oxidation behaviour of pure and wire reinforced Mo(Si,Ge)₂

Zeitsch (9) found, that with higher contents of MoGe₂ (40- 80 %) in MoSi₂ the oxidation rate is increased, but small amounts of MoGe₂ (5- 15 %) in MoSi₂ spoil the oxidation resistance insignificant, but avoid the upper mentioned 'pest reaction' in the temperature range below MoO₃ volatilisation, even if the porosity is more than 10 %.

Fig.17 and 18 show the lapses of weight for hot pressed specimens with MoGe₂ contents between 5 and 20 Mol/o at 1000 °C. Increasing MoGe₂ contents result in a higher mass loss depending on the volatilisation of GeO.

The well-known fast oxidation of niobium in air is represented in the upper part of Fig.19. Because of the small density of Nb₂O₅ compared to niobium, the oxide is growing out of a polished transversal cut (T = 1200 °C, t = 5'). The enlargement on the right side shows a small space between matrix and Nb₂O₅. The niobium is oxidized to Nb₂O₅ by uptake of oxygen and is growing anisotropically like extruded from an injection nozzle.

In spite of this result Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ composites show no oxidation of Nb at isothermal HTT up to 1600 °C even after crack formation by flexural strength measurement. Only thermal cycles (>1000) at 1100 °C can destroy samples with cracks (5). The beginning oxidation (900 °C, 10⁻⁶ bar air) is shown in Fig.19 bottom. The formed GeO is evaporated. In a pressure nearby vacuum GeO violently erupts out of the Ge-rich areas.

7. Thermal expansion measurements (CTE)

Experiments about the expansion coefficients of pure and reinforced Mo(Si, Ge)₂ hot pressed samples in all three dimensions gave significant differences (Fig.20). The CTE depends on the fibre content as well as on the direction parallel or transverse to fibre axis. Reinforced samples with a fibre volume content of 40/o Nb-wires show only low anisotropy, but samples without reinforcement exhibit an enormous anisotropy parallel and transverse to the hot pressing direction. This effect can only be explained by the inhomogeneous distribution of pressure in powders consisting of small grains. In case of reinforcement by prepreg layers of Nb-wires the distribution of pressure will be more homogeneous, because the layers are working like movable plugs.

8. Discussion and conclusion

In conventional composites a ductile material is reinforced by high modulus fibres. If strain to failure of the matrix exceeds that of the fibre the strengthening effect is mainly controlled by the volume fraction of the fibre ($\sigma_C \sim x_F \cdot \sigma_F$). In case of a brittle matrix the composite strength is expected to be controlled by the strain to failure of the matrix and the fibre strength will be used only partially. The experiment shows that such a result has not been found in this case, but the toughness of the composite is more than two times higher than that of pure material. The Ge containing interlayer causes a radial crack deviation and crack energy absorption so that the initially formed microcracks in the brittle matrix will not propagate into the reinforcing wires and the fracture is retarded until the strain to failure of the wires is exceeded.

The rule of mixture is not valid for reinforcement of Mo(Si,Ge)₂ by niobium. Preliminary tests showed that an improvement of flexural strength of pure Mo(Si,Ge)₂ can already be obtained in case of partial reinforcement with only one or two layers of Nb-wire prepreps of the tensile stress side. The improvement of flexural strength was about 50 % compared with unreinforced

Fig. 18 Specific weight change of pure bulk material with different germanide content at 1000 °C under air (long-time measurement)

Fig. 19 Top: Anisotropic oxidation behaviour of Nb-wire
 Bottom: GeO-evaporation during oxidation of a Nb/Mo(Si,Ge)₂ composite (1200 °C and 10⁻⁶ bar)

Fig. 20 Thermal expansion coefficients of hot pressed samples versus wire content, measured for all three dimensions

Mo(Si,Ge)₂.

Small amounts of germanide in MoSi₂ spoil insignificantly the oxidation resistance but avoid the 'pest reaction' at low temperatures.

It was found that the germanide containing interlayer at the phase boundary between niobium and matrix is not only responsible for the toughening but leads furthermore to a strongly improved oxidation resistance of the reinforcing wire compared with the not protected one.

Nb-wire reinforced Mo(Si,Ge)₂ composites show nearly isotropic thermal expansion behaviour although the pure hot pressed samples show a remarkable anisotropy.

9. References

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